

YASHIL

**IQTISODIYOT
va
TARAQQIYOT**

*Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik,
ilmiy, ommabop jurnal*

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RIVOJLANTIRISHDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI,
IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA AUDITNING ROLI HAMDA
ISTIQBOLDAGI VAZIFALAR" MAVZUSIDAGI
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THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF RESOURCE SAVING IN AGRICULTURE

Mirzaev Batir

Candidate of Economic Sciences,
Associate Professor of the Institute of agricultural and agrotechnologies of Karakalpakstan

Djumabaeva Nurzada Torebekovna

Base doctoral student of the Institute of agricultural and agrotechnologies of Karakalpakstan

Abstract: This thesis examines the theoretical foundations of resource saving in agriculture, particularly in the process of cotton production. The study analyzes the role of material, human, financial, technological, land, water, and energy resources, as well as ways of using them efficiently. The importance of modern agrotechnologies, drip irrigation, renewable energy sources, and smart agriculture systems in resource conservation is substantiated. It is concluded that the rational use of resources is a key factor in ensuring sustainable agricultural development.

Key words: agriculture, resource saving, cotton production, land and water resources, smart agriculture, sustainable development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy ishda qishloq xo'jaligida, xususan, paxta yetishtirish jarayonida resurslarni tejashning nazariy asoslari yoritib berilgan. Tadqiqotda moddiy, inson, moliyaviy, texnologik, yer, suv va energiya resurslarining o'rni hamda ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari tahlil qilingan. Zamonaviy agrotexnologiyalar, tomchilatib sug'orish, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalari va "aqli qishloq xo'jaligi" tizimlarining resurslarni tejashdagi ahamiyati asoslab berilgan. Resurslardan oqilona foydalanish qishloq xo'jaligining barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlashda muhim omil ekanligi xulosa qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: qishloq xo'jaligi, resurslarni tejash, paxta yetishtirish, yer va suv resurslari, aqli qishloq xo'jaligi, barqaror rivojlanish.

Аннотация: В данной работе рассматриваются теоретические основы ресурсосбережения в сельском хозяйстве, в частности в процессе производства хлопка. Проанализирована роль материальных, трудовых, финансовых, технологических, земельных, водных и энергетических ресурсов, а также пути их эффективного использования. Обоснована значимость современных агротехнологий, капельного орошения, возобновляемых источников энергии и систем «умного сельского хозяйства» в обеспечении ресурсосбережения. Сделан вывод о том, что рациональное использование ресурсов является важным фактором устойчивого развития сельского хозяйства.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, ресурсосбережение, производство хлопка, земельные и водные ресурсы, умное сельское хозяйство, устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

The process of cotton production is one of the most important and widespread sectors of agriculture. In this process, the role and significance of resources are of particular importance, as they determine both the quality and quantity of the yield. The proper use of resources in cotton cultivation is essential for increasing agricultural profitability and ensuring sustainable development.

Main Part. Firstly, material resources are one of the main components of the cotton production process. Cotton seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides play a crucial role as key inputs. High-quality seeds ensure proper crop growth, fertilizers increase soil fertility, and pesticides help protect crops from diseases and pests.

Secondly, human resources are also of great importance in cotton production. Skilled workers participate in planting, maintaining, and harvesting cotton, and their experience and knowledge contribute to improving crop quality. Management specialists, in turn, play a key role in planning and controlling the production process [1].

Thirdly, financial resources are necessary for the development of cotton production. Investments and financial funds enable the introduction of new technologies and the expansion of production capacity. Through adequate financial resources, the application of modern agricultural methods increases overall efficiency.

Technological resources also occupy a special place in the cotton production process. Tractors, cotton harvesting machines, and other agricultural equipment are essential for efficient production. Modern technologies, such as smart agriculture methods, help maximize the efficient use of resources. As a result, the role and importance of resources in cotton production are decisive, as they are crucial for increasing yields, improving quality, and organizing the production process efficiently [2].

Directions of resource saving in agriculture. In the development of modern agriculture, the rational use and conservation of resources are among the most urgent issues. Along with meeting the growing food needs of the population, protecting natural resources and ensuring environmental sustainability are priority directions of contemporary agricultural policy. From this perspective, resource saving in agriculture requires large-scale scientific research and the implementation of practical mechanisms.

Resource saving primarily refers to the efficient and rational use of land, water, energy, fertilizers, seeds, and other agricultural inputs. In this regard, the introduction of modern agrotechnologies, the use of digital monitoring systems, energy-saving mechanisms, and automated management systems are of great importance. Especially under conditions of water scarcity, the widespread adoption of drip irrigation technologies can reduce water consumption by 30–50 percent.

Another important direction is the efficient use of land resources. Rather than developing non-traditional lands, increasing production volumes by improving productivity on existing farmland is considered more effective. This approach requires intensive farming methods, high-yield and disease-resistant crop varieties, and the scientifically based application of agrochemicals. At the same time, proper crop rotation systems play a significant role in maintaining long-term soil fertility.

Energy conservation also plays a key role in the sustainable development of agriculture. The use of renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and biogas helps reduce energy costs and limit negative environmental impacts. For example, the use of solar panels to supply energy for greenhouses ensures energy independence and increases economic efficiency.

In addition, resource saving can be achieved through “smart agriculture” systems based on modern information and communication technologies. Remote sensing, GPS systems, drones, and sensors provide real-time data on soil conditions, moisture levels, and plant growth. This approach helps reduce the excessive use of fertilizers, water, and pesticides while maintaining ecological balance in crop production [3].

One of the foundations of agricultural economics is natural resources. The most essential natural resources include land and water. Land is the main factor of production in agriculture, serving as an object of labor, a space for the location of various economic activities, a residential area for humans, and a habitat for flora and fauna. Land resources represent the total land surface, including other natural components such as forests, vegetation, living organisms, and inland water bodies.

Water bodies within land resources include lakes, ponds, canals, and ditches, while oceans, seas, and rivers are classified as water resources. The land and water resources of each country form the foundation of life for both nature and society. Moreover, land and water are interdependent and require each other to ensure sustainable existence and development [4].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Efficient and rational use of resources in agriculture is a key factor in ensuring sustainable development, increasing productivity, and maintaining ecological balance. In cotton production, the effective management of material, human, financial, technological, land, water, and energy resources directly influences production outcomes. The adoption of modern technologies, smart agriculture systems, and renewable energy sources contributes significantly to resource conservation and improved economic efficiency. Therefore, resource saving in agriculture is not only an economic necessity but also a crucial condition for environmental protection and long-term agricultural sustainability.

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EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

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